

TÙNGBÁ: A SOCIO-RELIGIOUS GOSPEL MUSIC

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Abstract

Tùngbá is a new style of gospel music which possesses some unique elements that makes it stand out of the existing gospel music styles. One of the uniqueness of the style is embedded on its ability to satisfy both religious and social musical needs of its numerous admirers. How can a gospel music be accepted by people of other faith? The paper, therefore, is an attempt to inquire into the intricacies of the elements that makes it accepted by its listeners irrespective of religious affiliations. Library and interview were the methods of data collection used to gather information for this study. The study shows that tùngbá gospel musicians use elements like rhythm, texts and eulogies to attract their fans to accept their music beyond Christianity. The paper concludes that musicians generally and those of gospel genre in particular should be creative enough to create atmosphere of peace amongst the populace, especially in the area of religion. When this is achieved, we would have a better interaction amongst different religious faith.

Keywords: Tùngbá, gospel, other faith, religious affiliation.